

REFINING STUDENTS' ESSAY CONTENTS

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ABSTRACT

Writing a good English academic essay is generally a demanding task for most Vietnamese-speaking EFL college students because they have to develop writing skills on a regular practice basis with much attention and effort, not just in class but also behind class time on their own. This is by no means appealing to most Vietnamese students and consequently they actually face difficulties in performing English essay assignments. The present paper investigates timed-exam essays written by English majors of upper-intermediate level at Dong Thap University (Dong Thap province in the Mekong Delta, South West of Vietnam) over the past years. It pinpoints shortcomings in these exam-essays and thereby makes suggestions for students' improved strategies and skills in designing and expressing essay contents in the principal parts of introduction, body and concluding paragraphs. The results reveal that for the introduction many essays did not indicate how the topic is going to be developed (whether the essay is going to discuss causes, effects, reasons or examples; whether the essay is going to classify, describe, narrate or explain a process). Meanwhile, quite a number of the essays lacked a clear topic sentence in each body paragraph and sufficient supporting material. The essay conclusion should also be improved in some way.

Key words: Essay, paragraph, topic sentence, introduction, conclusion.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is generally agreed that being able to write sound English essays of various types (i.e. compare-and-contrast, classification, process analysis, cause-and-effect, argumentative) is one of the major targets for EFL students at tertiary education. Strictly speaking, the target requires students to work very hard on a regular practice basis to acquire related subskills of academic writing because the task of writing an essay in another language is quite a complex process. Definitely, they have to develop not only linguistic knowledge of the English language (*phonology, vocabulary, grammar and punctuation*), but also competences of rhetorical conventions at the text level in order to organize and express relevant ideas/contents in an appropriate way. As a result, Vietnamese-speaking EFL students generally have to face a number of problems due to tangible discrepancies in wording and discourse patterns between English and Vietnamese. In reality, these problems can be explicitly revealed in common weaknesses or errors committed by students in their English essays, especially during their mid-stages of the language acquisition.

It is, therefore, of great significance to examine the weaknesses in question to raise students' awareness and in some ways help them fix these weaknesses to improve the quality of essays

before they become fossilized (i.e. *Linguistic items, rules and subsystems which speakers of a particular native language will tend to keep in their interlanguage relative to a particular target language, no matter what the age of the learner or amount of explanation and instruction he receives in the target language*, Selinker 1984:36). And more importantly, this reflective approach is part of the teaching/learning discipline to assist students to well acquire the required skills at the end of the target training program, and subsequently they are expected to be confident enough to cope with different English essay writings in prospective careers as well as further education related to the English language because “*writing is important in studying all subjects and in all professions. Only by writing well can you give a good account of yourself as a student, and when applying for employment, and in a career when you write letters, instructions and reports. It is by your writing that others know you.*” (Barrass, 1995:2)

As a consequence, this limited paper is aimed to investigate weaknesses and accordingly suggest the “can-improve” points found in English essays written by English majors of upper-intermediate level in their real writing exams at *Dong Thap University* (Dong Thap province in the Mekong Delta, South West of Vietnam) over the past years. The essay *extracts* in the next parts are all selected from the real timed-exam papers (having been marked and annotated by two teachers of English in charge of the writing courses). All the extracts are rewritten below as in their original form (sometimes in italics and bold type just in the case of points in discussion) for illustrations and analysis.

Rarely do students have the opportunity to look back at their real exam papers (final-term ones) under Vietnam’s current education system. Thus, it will substantially benefit student writers if this opportunity is realized (by their teachers) in some instructive way to allow them to see what they have gained and what should be improved from the observed weaknesses regarding language skills, contents and critical thinking.

2 FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Since language use errors of *tense system, articles and prepositions* made by Vietnamese-speaking EFL students in their English compositions and other task types have been more or less widely examined by Vietnamese researchers and teachers of English in the past years (Phạm Đăng Bình, 2002; Trần Thị Minh Phượng, 2005; Đỗ Minh Hùng, 2007; Đỗ Minh Hùng, 2014; etc.), the present paper is to focus more on the content level.

Theoretically, an academic essay always has 3 separated parts: one introductory paragraph, two or more body paragraphs and one concluding. As a result, the sections below will discuss each part respectively. (However, it is impossible to cover everything related to essay contents within a limited paper like the present one. Rather, selected extracts will be rewritten for discussion on salient points.)

2.1 Introductory paragraph

As a general rule, the introductory paragraph (introduction) is the first one in an academic essay. It could be approached in different ways such as *background information* slowly leading to the

thesis statement; a *quotation* from a well-known saying, or an appropriate remark by a famous person; a *definition/explanation* preparing the reader for applications and examples of the concept or term being defined; a *problem-solution* raising the problem and suggesting the solution; or a *summary* for an analysis/discussion of what has been summarized.

A good introduction, whatever approach it applies, should include the following elements (Smalley & Ruetten, 1986:142; Blass & Pike-Baky, 2007:162; Gaetz & Phadke, 2009: 181):

- (1) introducing the essay topic;
- (2) containing the thesis statement/sentence;
- (3) indicating how the topic is going to be developed (whether the essay is going to discuss causes, effects, reasons or examples; whether the essay is going to classify, describe, narrate or explain a process);
- (4) being interesting enough to make the reader want to continue reading.

Accordingly, the first problem concerning the introduction is that many investigated essays failed to address element (3) very clearly as expected. Take Extract 1, for instance:

Extract 1:

We are living in the age of technology. The birth of Internet in modern time has actually changed everything: the way people communicate with each other, the way people entertain, the way people study, and the way people do business. Some people say that the Internet provides people with a lot of valuable information. However, in my point of view, accessing too much information creates many problems.

One reason creating these problems is that information on the Internet comes from various sources. Almost all people are allowed to upload information to the Internet. Maybe this information is uploaded by a famous person or a well-known group, and maybe that information is uploaded by a strange boy or girl who has nothing to do in his free time but upload useless things to the Internet. Information on the Internet also sent by opposed person who always desires to fight against the government and the society. If people searching for information on the Internet are not strong enough, not knowledgeable enough, how can they distinguish these various kinds of information and choose the rightful source?

Accessing so much information creates problems also because it makes people become dependent completely on the information of the Internet sources...

Since the essay (Extract 1) was intended to explain the causes of the concerned problems, it certainly makes sense to add something indicating element (3) to the end of the introduction in a more explicit way as a purposeful indicator of shift from the introduction to body paragraphs, such as “*The next paragraphs will examine some major causes of the problems*”; “*Several reasons for the problems are discussed in details below*”; “*The next parts are going to point out causes and also suggest solutions to the concerned problems*”; “*Certainly, there are reasons for these problems and they will be uncovered one by one as follows*”.

Other essays not only lacked element (3), but also provided an unclear thesis statement of element (2) in the introduction. Moreover, with the *background information* approach (i.e. general-to-specific → thesis statement) to create a high level of interest, it is a good idea not to put the thesis statement right at the beginning of the introduction (Smalley & Ruetten, 1986:142; Pike-Baky & Blass, 2007:73). As a consequence, such introductions as Extract 2 (about the topic of the qualities of a successful teacher of English) should be improved.

Extract 2:

Qualities that make a successful teacher of English are self-confident, having good knowledge and working hard. We must love our students and our jobs. We have to understand what our students needs and solve the problems with them.

[Suggested version 1→Teachers is generally one of the fundamental factors to make a successful education in all countries. However, they themselves have to develop a number of related qualities to play the given role and expectedly succeed in their career. In my opinion, a successful teacher of English is primarily required to have the qualities of self-confidence, diligence, love for students and job. In addition, they should understand students' needs and help them solve problems if needed. These qualities will be discussed and illustrated in the following parts.]

[Suggested version 2→ As a teacher of English in the future, I am very concerned about the question of "What qualities make a successful teacher of English?" To the best of my present knowledge, to do the job successfully a teacher of English should acquire those qualities of self-confidence, devotion, commitment and love for job and students. The teacher is also expected to understand students' needs and readily help them solve problems if needed. The following will address these qualities in detail.]

Meanwhile, the introduction of a comparison-contrast essay should particularly include *items/points/aspects* for comparison and contrast, signaling the foci in the body paragraphs of the essay. The introduction below (Extract 3) could be followed by “... and differences *in terms of contents, formats and audiences*, which will be compared and contrasted for more details in the next parts of the essay”, or “Compared and contrasted details in the aspects of content, format and audience between these two very useful media are discussed respectively below”.

Extract 3:

Television and newspapers are two very important means of the mass media. Nowadays most people have at least one television set in their families. Newspapers can be found in most families and offices. Watching television and reading newspapers are two popular habits of modern people. Television and newspapers have both similarities and differences.

It is also unwise to write a lengthy but unproductive introduction with redundant information and lexical repetitions like the following:

Extract 4:

Nowadays students in secondary schools have to study many subjects. Among them are the subjects relating to science subjects, natural subjects... Besides, students have to learn the subjects which help them to develop their creativity such as art and music. Now some people are suspicious of whether students in secondary schools should be required to learn art and music at school or not. They argue that art and music are unimportant subjects. Therefore, their children don't need to pay attention to these subjects. In contrast, I personally agree with those who agree that students in secondary schools should be required learn art and music at school. There are many reasons for my point of view.

[Suggested version → Secondary school students have to learn the core line subjects for life knowledge and skills, including maths, social-natural sciences, foreign language and literature. In the other line, they also learn art and music for creativity or aesthetic development. Yet, some people are now suspicious of the necessity of the latter line subjects at secondary school level as they appear to be insignificant. But I do agree that these two subjects should be present in the school schedule for many reasons to be clarified in the following section.]

As it turns out, the final sentence in the suggested version indicates clearly both the writer's opinion/viewpoint in the thesis statement and how the topic is going to be developed. In particular, there is no need for "*Therefore, their children don't need to pay attention to these subjects*" because it does not rightly serve the thesis statement in this case (unless the topic is about parents' and students' reactions/attitudes towards art and music subjects at secondary schools). As a result, together with other unnecessary repetitions removed and lexical revisions, it indeed helps condense the introduction sufficiently and invitingly.

2.2 Body paragraphs

As mentioned earlier an academic essay needs from about two to four body paragraphs making *the heart of the essay*. They are supposed to prove the thesis statement in the introduction and should encompass the following characteristics (Smalley & Ruetten, 1986:146; Zemach & Rumisek, 2005: 56; Rolls & Wignell, 2013: 55):

- (1) All body paragraphs should be balanced and distinct (i.e. they don't overlap but have the same degree of importance in relation to the essay central idea);
- (2) Each body paragraph discusses *one aspect* of the main topic;
- (3) The controlling idea in the body paragraph should *echo the central idea* in the thesis statement of the introduction;
- (4) The body paragraph should have coherence and unity; the sentences move smoothly from one to the other.

Furthermore, a well-developed body paragraph must have (Blass and Pike-Baky, 2007: 91): (i) the topic sentence expressing the main idea; (ii) the bridge explaining the main idea and connects it to the supporting material; (iii) the supporting material including examples, facts, statistics, or

an anecdote (a short story about a person or event that illustrates or dramatizes a point); (iv) the conclusion reminding the reader of the main idea and concluding the paragraph. Also, it often includes an interpretation (or analysis) of the supporting material.

Look at Extract 5 of the first body paragraph about the usefulnesses/advantages of Internet below:

Extract 5:

Internet is for not only information but also beautiful sights and new people. People all over the world are connected together by Internet. Internet helps us understand about lifestyles and culture of people around us although we never go to there. It also helps us understand that countries' status are that it is rich or poor. Thanks to Internet we can see strangely animals or things we have never known before. Finally, Internet is very helpful for our studying. We can study any language on it. For example, English, Chinese, French. People may be happy when they learn many things around them. Internet also helps us improve our skills in many other fields such as communication, cooking, creativity, lifestyle.

It apparently lacks at least the topic sentence and the conclusion as well although it addresses one aspect of the essay main topic (i.e. the good points of Internet). The paragraph would look better with such a topic sentence at the beginning like “*A great number of advantages could be thought of thanks to Internet. The tool brings us not only*”; “*Internet benefits human beings in numerous ways. It provides not only ...*”; “*We can benefit from Internet in so many ways. It serves us with not only ...*”; “*Internet is definitely a very useful instrument to us. This powerfully-increasing instrument can satisfy human needs for not only...* ” and so on. Likewise, the concluding sentence at the end should most likely read “*Obviously, Internet is advantageous to human beings*”; “*As a result, this potentially great tool would certainly make our life better in various ways*” and the like.

Another marked problem is that this body paragraph did not provide sufficient supporting material, namely specific examples, facts, or anecdotes. It should have given *specific* examples of beautiful sights (such as *the Great Wall of China, the city of Paris, the Hanging Gardens of Babylon, the Great Pyramid of Giza*), strange animals (like *kiwis, kangaroos, snakes, sun fish*) or things that one could get from Internet with specific different websites for reference.

Similarly, in Extract 6, the topic sentence “*Marrying a foreigner, of course, is very good*” is present, but somehow incomplete because it should have indicated “*How/In what specific ways is it good?*” prior to providing supporting details (Suggested → *Marrying a foreigner, of course, is very good for one to acquire knowledge about another country, culture and language.*) Additionally, the concluding sentence of this body paragraph has been missed (Suggested → “*Thus, cross-culture marriage is generally beneficial in several ways*”; “*Accordingly, it is clear that cross-culture marriage is good enough for practice*”; “*There is no doubt that bicultural marriage is encouraging*”).

Extract 6:

Marrying a foreigner, of course, is very good. A girl can broaden her knowledge as well as travel in other countries. For instance, she loves to live in Canada and fortunately, she loves and marries a Canadian so that she can live there. In addition, she can visit beautiful Quebec City with old buildings and splendid restaurants. Meanwhile, she can discover and know about its history, such as how and when it was established. Furthermore, she can also know another language as well as some characteristics of that country. For example, she can know Canada has two major official languages such as French and English.

In addition, quite a large number of the essays failed to meet characteristic (4) mentioned above, i.e. unity and coherence within each body paragraph. Take a look at Extract 7, the first body paragraph (of an essay analyzing factors that contribute to success as a company leader).

Extract 7:

First of all, for success a leader should be modest and knowledgeable. Because when a leader is modest, others respect him or her a lot. Sometimes a modest person is ready to learn. They can listen to other people's opinions and take the knowledge from people around them. Also, a leader has to get a good knowledge in the fields which he or she needs to offer good strategies for the company's development or that leader is ready to solve any obstacles or difficulties that the company is facing in order for the company to get over the problems ahead.

The topic sentence is clear, but the ideas expressed in the paragraph are not very unified in spite of the fact that three key terms *leader*, *modest*, *knowledge* are repeated several times throughout the paragraph. First, *respect* from other people does not always ensure *success* in leadership although it can help in some way. Then, the idea “*Sometimes a modest person is ready to learn*” does not result from the previous one, and nor does it serve well the topic sentence because of the concept “sometimes” there. What is more, the presence of both “modest” and “knowledgeable” in such a single paragraph makes it hard to develop the topic sentence in a linear, profound way. Roughly speaking, the paragraph aims to express that *modesty* mostly allows a leader to honestly listen to and thereby learns from other people, especially his own staffs/employees' opinions, recommendations, advice or innovations (rather than always thinking his own are the best and turns down all other valid ideas). In this way, the leader can synthesize, analyze, weigh up, and filter these various inputs, and possibly comes up with appropriate decisions and action strategies for obstacles to be solved or plans to fulfill, and thus fosters his company's development. Simultaneously, step by step he acquires relevant knowledge, skills and mutual/collective spirit in leadership. All these processes contribute to the leader's success in the long run.

As a result, it is better to cope with one aspect/point in each paragraph of an academic essay; thus the paragraph should read:

[Suggested → First of all, for success a leader should be modest. This quality will greatly help him/her to readily listen to and learn from other people's ideas or opinions. Thereby, he is likely to make better decisions and critical strategies for action programs or against

accidental difficulties successfully, leading the company to achieve its plans for progress because “two heads are better than one”. Moreover, taking in other people’s advice for thorough consideration, especially prior to important decisions, the leader not only avoids making serious mistakes, but also has opportunity to gain more management knowledge and skills, which paves his way for successful leadership. Thus, modesty is substantially important for a company leader’s success.]

Lack of unity and coherence can also be seen in Extract 8, one body paragraph explaining the cause of *school violence*.

Extract 8:

Secondly, school violence is also caused by a lack of interest from parents. Some families have to go far away from home to earn money for the cost of their life. They are too busy to care for their children as well as possible. Their minds just think that they should earn more money for their children, then their children will have full life and their children will be happy. It is wrong. Considerations of parents to their children is very important their children will be easy to get faults when they get careless from their parents and fall down to evil society too because they can listen to the bad people around their life to take advantage of them such as the money. Moreover, if the children live in bad society, they will also be easy to be bad children because they follow the actions that they saw everyday in their life, for example thieves or fightings.

[Suggested → Secondly, school violence is also caused by parents’ lack of care for their children. Since they have to work far from home for living, parents have little time spending with and taking care of their children. Moreover, they wrongly think that decent money will provide children with full life of happiness. They however should recognize that parents’ sufficient care will substantially help children stay away from social evils, badly influential characters and violent behaviors, especially severe rows and fightings which may tempt children to do the same at school whenever they are in an angry mood or get annoyed about something. Thus, parents’ good care for their children significantly helps prevent school violence.

Another argument strategy students should be encouraged to apply is *refuting* (i.e. to prove one’s reasons/points are more valid or superior to the opponent’s ones; or to show that something is wrong/erroneous). The strategy is commonly used in argumentative essays (Smalley & Ruetten, 1986:335). However, it is rarely found among the investigated essay papers. To argue more persuasively, for instance, in the topic of Extract 6 above, with another body paragraph preceding the conclusion as rewritten below, the writer may first *concede* the inevitable problems of language and culture distances, and then assert that these problems are by no means long-lasting and could be step by step strengthened out by both parties’ efforts over months or years. Meanwhile, the related benefits (as accommodated in the body paragraphs) are definitely long-termed and even forever, such as the ability to speak another language and rewarding experiences

to live in another culture. As a result, the cross-cultural marriage on the basis of true love has good reasons to take its place.

Extract 6 (continued):

In short, marrying a foreigner is good because it may be an interesting experience in human life. However, true love is always a need in marriage so that if someone wants to marry, he or she must love each other. When they have true love, they will have happy life even though they have different cultures, customs and languages.

2.3 Concluding paragraph

Like the introductory and body paragraphs, concluding paragraph has its own characteristics, looking like the following model (Pike-Baky & Blass, 2007:116):

Look back at Extract 6 (continued), the first sentence with the restatement of the thesis is fine, but the next sentence sounds redundant because the idea could be accommodated in the first one and instead, a more general statement should take place there, like “*In short, marrying a foreigner on a true love basis is certainly good because it may turn out to be an interesting experience and brings about several benefits as mentioned above. True love is essential to all types of human marriage, especially the cross-cultural one because it is the true love that helps concerned people gradually and successfully overcome inevitable obstacles with regard to distances in culture, custom and language.*”

Similarly, the concluding paragraph of Extract 1 below can improve in some way:

Extract 1 (continued)

The age of Internet opens new horizon. However, accessing to so much information on the Internet may create many problems as it contains various kinds of information from various sources and it also limits people creativity. Therefore, people should use the Internet in a reasonable way to get the most benefit from it.

The first sentence is redundant because it is too general. The second sentence should be more assertive by deleting the modal “may” or replacing it by such emphatic phrases as “does create”, “definitely/certainly causes ...”, “ultimately/in the long run leads to/results in/has to deal with/faces...”. And as such, the demand/advice/recommendation expressed in the third sentence sounds stronger and appealing.

Extract 9 is the concluding paragraph of one essay on the exam question “*Some people prefer to get up early in the morning and start the day’s work. Others prefer to get up later in the day and work until late at night. Which do you prefer?*”.

Extract 9:

In sum, getting up early in the morning and starting the day’s work is actually a good habit because it helps people work effectively, provides effectiveness of refreshment, and builds up people’s brains. Once possessing a good working habit, which includes working and relaxing reasonably, people are likely to get success in their life.

The first sentence does its job very well in reasserting the main points discussed and the thesis in different words. The paragraph, however, would sound better with such more general statements to follow the first sentence as “*This good working habit should be practiced and customized, especially by young people and students with their whole careers in the coming future*”, or “*As a result, there are definitely good reasons for everyone to practice the habit*”. The inserted sentence in the middle has three goals: (i) to bridge the first and the last sentence (from *more* to *most* general statements); (ii) to make the paragraph coherent “... *actually a good habit* (first sentence)... *This good working habit* (inserted sentence)... *Once possessing a good working habit* (last sentence)”; and (iii) to make a recommendation or emphasize a relevant action to the reader, as usually required in an argumentative essay (Smalley & Ruetten, 1986:335; Zemach & Rumisek, 2005:74).

3 CONCLUSION

Being aware of the complexity of writing an English academic essay and authentic problems faced by EFL Vietnamese students, this paper investigated exam essays written by English majors at Dong Thap University. It has addressed all three principal sections of an essay: introduction, body and conclusion with several illustrations, shortcoming analyses in details and revisions for improvement regarding the contents and language use as well (especially avoiding redundant lexical or sentential repetitions). As a result, it is suggested that together with other regular in-class activities (i.e. presenting essay models, processes of writing, brainstorming, draft-writing, editing and so on) teachers should purposely help students not only correct linguistic errors but refine essay contents as well, particularly at the feedback stage, where students are given back their own test/exam papers (both mid-term and final one) for revision, correction and modification on the self or individual basis followed by the peer or group exchange if time is permitted. Subsequently, teachers may ask students to rewrite the essay in class (if possible) or at home. Then, those who resubmit the new version of essay papers (in paper or electronic format) will get extra marks for the term grade. On the regular practice basis in this way, students are likely not only to improve essay quality but also profoundly acquire the related skills and develop autonomous learning in the long run.

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